

THE EFFECT OF FIBRE SURFACE TREATMENTS DURING CFRP PRODUCTION ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are not widely recycled at the end-to-life stage due to challenges associated with the quality of recycled fibres. In the pyrolysis recycling approach, carbon fibres experience reduction in the fibre tensile strength due to oxidative degradation. The variation in CFRPs further leads to inconsistent quality of recycled carbon fibres. The different fibre surface treatments could be part of this complication. It is unclear whether fibre surface treatments would alter the thermal behaviours of CFRP during recycling and lead to different quality of recycled carbon fibres. This study investigates the effects of electrochemical oxidation in ammonium bicarbonate ($(\text{NH}_4)\text{HCO}_3$) bath and fibre sizing with epoxy resin 834 on the quality of recycled carbon fibres. Lab-scale recycling trials were carried out on four types of CFRPs with different fibre surface treatments. The results show that both treatments have limited effects on the thermal characteristics of CFRP during the pyrolysis recycling processes. Recycled carbon fibres from CFRP with these fibre surface treatments experienced a 5.1% - 12.8% reduction in tensile strength compared to the virgin fibres. This study shows that fibre electrochemical oxidation in ammonium bicarbonate and sizing with epoxy 834 during CFRP production have a minor impact on the tensile strength of recycled carbon fibres.

1 INTRODUCTION

The lack of recycling of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) leads to environmental challenges and loss of material value. Landfilling is relatively cheap and hence, the most common end-of-life disposal method for CFRPs [1–3]. However, CFRPs remain undegraded in the landfill, due to the corrosion resistance of CFRPs, particularly the carbon fibres [3]. In addition to environmental challenges, the lack of recycling of CFRPs leads to a loss of material value for the carbon fibres. The production process of virgin carbon fibres is energy intensive (183-286MJ/kg) [4, 5]. The embodied energy of carbon fibre as well as its reinforcement value are lost due to the lack of recycling.

The currently used pyrolysis approach for CFRP recycling has led to reduced tensile strength of carbon fibres. The one CFRP recycling approach being studied and industrialised is the two-step pyrolysis approach [5], [6]. In this approach, CFRPs are first treated in the inert atmosphere to pyrolyse the polymer resin matrix, followed by a char removal process in an oxidative environment. During the char removal process, the char residue is oxidised while the remaining carbon fibres ideally remain undamaged. However, a 10-20% reduction in the tensile strength of carbon fibres during the pyrolysis recycling process has been reported from researchers and industrial recyclers [5, 7, 8]. Oxidative degradation reduces the tensile strength of carbon fibres during the pyrolysis recycling approach.

The variations of CFRPs lead to inconsistent strength reduction in recycled carbon fibres. Different types of CFRPs have different thermal behaviours, due to the different thermal characteristics of the constituent materials [1, 9, 10]. When different CFRPs are mixed in the recycling stage, optimisation of processing parameters to recover CFs with minimal reduction in fibre tensile strength and minimal resin residue becomes difficult. The amount of reduction in the fibre tensile strength becomes inconsistent.

It is unclear if different fibre surface treatments in the production of CFRP also lead to different levels of strength reduction during the recycling of carbon fibres. Fibre surface treatments aim at improving wettability of the carbon fibre surface and hence achieving a greater interfacial shear strength between the fibres and the matrix after resin impregnation [11]. One fibre surface treatment method is the electrochemical oxidation of carbon fibre surface, which introduces polar functional groups onto the surface of carbon fibres [12]. Another fibre surface treatment is sizing, which introduces a thin layer of resin on the fibre surface [12]. Despite the benefits of fibre surface treatments on the quality of CFRP, the impacts of these treatments on the end-of-life phase of CFRP are unclear. There is a lack of understanding on whether the fibre surface treatments will affect the thermal behaviours of CFRP during recycling, and more importantly, the quality of the recycled carbon fibres.

This study aims at investigating the effects of fibre surface treatments during the production of CFRP on the tensile strength of the recycled carbon fibres. Four types of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin with different conditions of fibre surface oxidation and fibre sizing were chosen for the investigation. Thermogravimetric analysis, lab-scale recycling trials and single fibre tensile testing were the main methods of this study. This study provides insights on whether the two fibre surface treatment methods affect the thermal characteristics of CFRP during recycling and cause inconsistent quality of the recycled carbon fibres.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Four types of CFRP laminate with different fibre surface treatment conditions were studied. Each type consisted of six layers of unidirectional carbon fibre produced by Carbon Nexus and RIM 935 epoxy resin cured with RIMH 937 hardener [14]. The fibre surface oxidation method involves submerging carbon fibres in an oxidation bath of ammonium bicarbonate ($(\text{NH}_4)\text{HCO}_3$) and conducting current through the bath [14]. The sizing method involves submerging carbon fibres in a mixture of Epoxy 834 resin and water to introduce the sizing layer on the fibre surface [14]. In this study, two processing parameters were varied: the oxidation current amperage for fibre surface oxidation, and the part ratio between epoxy 834 and water for sizing. The variation of the processing parameters is shown in Table 1. A control experiment to analyse the effects of these two treatment methods was conducted with these processing parameters being the only variables across the four samples.

Sample Number	Oxidation current (A)	Sizing ratio (epoxy 834: water)
1	0	Unsize
2	3.4	Unsize
3	0	1:15
4	3.4	1:15

Table 1: Fibre surface oxidation and sizing conditions of the samples.

2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted to understand the thermal characteristics of the CFRPs. Three samples with a mass ranging from 30mg to 40mg were taken from the left end, middle and the right end of each CFRP laminate bar for analysis (Figure 1). The instrument used for TGA was NETZSCH STA 449 F3 Jupiter. The first step of the analysis involved a temperature ramp from 50°C to 1000°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min, under a constant flow of nitrogen at 60mL/min. This step aims at investigating the onset decomposition temperature of the epoxy resin matrix, as well as the sizing layer in sample 3 and 4. In the second step of the analysis, the remaining solid materials from the first step were heated from 50°C to 1000°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min, under a constant air flow at 200mL/min. This step aims at investigating the temperatures for the oxidation of the pyrolytic char residue and the carbon fibres. The analysis settings were consistent with previous studies using TGA to

understand the thermal behaviours of CFRP [10, 15, 16]. NETZSCH Proteus software was used for graphic analysis of the TGA results to understand the aforementioned thermal characteristics.

Figure 1: CFRP laminate bar (sample 1) and the sampling areas for TGA.

2.3 Burn-off test

Burn-off test was conducted to determine the carbon fibre content in the samples. The standard burn-off method for carbon fibre determination used by the Ford Motor Company was used. A sample weighing at around 2.5g was cut from each type of material. The sample mass M_0 was measured with an analytical balance and recorded to four decimal places. The sample was then loosely wrapped with aluminium foil. The mass of the sample along with the foil M_1 was measured again and recorded to four decimal places. The wrapped sample was then placed in a muffle furnace. The temperature of the muffle furnace was increased to $475^\circ\text{C} \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. After 4-5 hours of holding time at $475^\circ\text{C} \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$, the wrapped sample was removed from the furnace and cooled to room temperature. The final mass of the sample with the aluminium foil M_2 was measured and recorded to four decimal places. The carbon fibre mass fraction in the sample was calculated by Equation (1):

$$CF\% = (M_1 - M_2) / M_0 * 100\% \quad (1)$$

2.4 Lab-scale recycling

Lab-scale recycling was performed in a tube furnace to recover fibres from the CFRP laminates. The instrument used was a GSL-1100X tube furnace supplied by MTI Corporation with a 40mm-diameter quartz reaction tube (Figure 2). One sample with a length of 36mm and a width of around 4mm was cut from each type of CFRP laminate, placed in an alumina crucible and inserted into the furnace tube for recycling.

The recycling procedure was based on the two-step pyrolysis recycling procedure for CFRP in the industry, which starts with the pyrolysis of the polymer resin matrix and finishes with a char removal process. Recycling parameters including the processing temperature, heating rate, gas flow rate, processing time for each step of the recycling process were determined from the results of TGA. Firstly, the temperature at maximum oxidation rate of char residue was determined to be the processing temperature. The processing temperature was constant throughout the recycling processes, including the pyrolysis and the char removal steps. The heating rate of the tube furnace was set to be the same as that in the TGA, in order to have comparable heating scenarios. The processing time for the pyrolysis step was determined to achieve complete decomposition of the polymer resin. The processing time for the char removal step was determined to achieve maximal removal of the pyrolytic char with minimal fibre degradation. Argon gas was used as purge gas for the pyrolysis process and compressed air was used for the char removal process. The volumetric gas flow rate in each step was determined by scaling up the volumetric gas flow rate during TGA based on the diameter ratio between the TGA heating chamber and the recycling furnace tube. The furnace was programmed to execute the recycling procedure.

Figure 2: GSL-1100X tube furnace for CFRP lab-scale recycling.

2.5 Single fibre tensile test

Single fibre tensile tests were performed to measure the tensile strength of the recycled carbon fibres. The testing procedure was in accordance with ASTM D3379. Paper tabs (10mm * 60mm) with a centred 20mm-long slot were made out of thin paper (Figure 3a). 10 single fibre filaments were randomly sampled from each type of recycled carbon fibres for testing. Under an optical microscope, each fibre was carefully mounted on a paper tab with cyanoacrylate adhesive securing the fibre at both ends of the slot. The Instron 4505 machine was used for the tensile testing. The two ends of the paper tab were clamped up to the edge of the slot (Figure 3). Before the tests commenced, the paper tab was carefully cut at the middle of the slot, leaving only the fibre subjected to load. A 10N load cell was used for the testing and the speed of the crosshead was 0.2mm/min. Based on the load-extension curve from the tensile tests and the predetermined average diameter of each type of recycled carbon fibre, the single fibre tensile strength was calculated.

Figure 3: A recycled CF filament mounted on a paper tab clamped on the Instron machine.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Thermal characteristics

TGA results show the thermal behaviours of the CFRP materials during the pyrolysis step of the recycling process. Figure 4(a) shows the average TGA curve and the average differential temperature gradient (DTG) curve of sample 1 in inert atmosphere. For sample 1, the sample mass remains constant until the temperature rises to $309.0 \pm 1.1^\circ\text{C}$. Beyond this temperature threshold, the sample mass starts to reduce and eventually reaches $44.7 \pm 2.6\%$ of the original level. At this stage, the cross-linked epoxy resin molecules in the matrix thermally break down into organic compounds with smaller molecular weight and solid char residue. The sample mass remains unchanged as the temperature continues to rise, which is expected since the remaining carbon fibres do not experience mass loss in inert environment.

TGA results also demonstrated the two-stage mass loss of the remaining mixture of char residue and carbon fibres during the char removal step. For sample 1, the first stage of the mass loss occurs at 509.3

$\pm 8.8^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 4(b)). At this stage, the char residue, which mainly consists of amorphous carbon, oxidises into carbon dioxide. While the carbon fibres with crystalline structure are not oxidised at this temperature. The second stage of mass loss begins at $718.0 \pm 5.1^\circ\text{C}$. At this stage, the remaining carbon fibres experience oxidation with the oxygen in the air. Eventually, 100% mass loss is reached as all carbon fibres are oxidised to carbon dioxide.

Figure 4: TGA (dash line) and DTG (solid line) curve of the sample 1 during the pyrolysis step (a) and the char-carbon fibre mixture during the char removal step (b).

By analysing the TGA results, the thermal characteristics of the samples during recycling were determined. These characteristics include the onset temperature for resin decomposition T_{ro} , the onset temperature for char oxidation T_{co} , the temperature at the maximum char oxidation rate T_{cm} and the onset temperature for fibre oxidation T_{fo} (Figure 5). The average value for each characteristic was calculated from three replicates for each material, as discussed in Section 2.2. The average T_{ro} of the four samples are within a 1.1°C (0.26%) difference (Figure 5(a)). The average T_{fo} are within a 7.0°C (1.0%) difference across the four samples (Figure 5(d)). It indicates a minor impact of the two fibre surface treatments on the thermal stability of the RIM 935 epoxy resin matrix and the carbon fibres. In contrast, the variation in the characteristics of the pyrolytic char residues T_{co} and T_{cm} across the four samples reaches 6.2% and 3.4%, respectively (Figure 5(b) and 5(c)). Nonetheless, at this stage with a sample size of three, it is difficult to understand the significance of the impact on the pyrolytic char residue as a result of fibre surface treatments. Statistical analysis based on a larger sample size is necessary.

Figure 5: Thermal characteristics of CFRP laminate samples during recycling (three replicates for each sample).

3.2 Recycling experiment

Processing parameters for the recycling of each type of CFRP were determined. These parameters are tabulated in Table 3 for comparison. As mentioned in section 2.4, the temperature at the maximum char oxidation rate is set to be the processing temperature. The processing temperature varies within a 19.3°C (3.4%) range in the four samples. The time needed to recycle CFRP with and without fibre surface treatments is the same, which is under expectation. Because of the small sample volume (less than 125mm³) for TGA, the temperature variation across the sample thickness was negligible. Hence the difference in interfacial heat transfer efficiency as a result of fibre surface treatments had a minor impact on the processing time. Further study could focus on the relationship between sample volume and the processing time, which will generate insights more applicable to industrial scenarios.

Sample Number	Processing temperature (°C)	Heating rate (°C/min)	Step 1: Pyrolysis		Step 2: Char removal	
			Time (min)	Argon flow rate (mL/min)	Time (min)	Air flow rate (mL/min)
1	554.6	10	100	220	20	730
2	562.4					
3	573.9					
4	565.6					

Table 2: Recycling parameters for the four types of CFRP.

Recycling of the CFRPs was conducted with the processing parameters in Table 3. Figure 6 shows a piece of the CFRP laminate before recycling (a) and the recycled carbon fibres (b). The recycled carbon fibres were in their original architecture immediately after the recycling process. But the fibre architecture easily fell apart during handling and became fluffy and unorganised. By visual inspection under an optical microscope (up to 50X), fibre filaments were separated with one another. The mass of the recycled carbon fibres ranged from 98.05% to 101.61% of the expected fibre content in the original CFRP laminate as determined from the burn-off test. This indicates that recycled carbon fibres with minimal resin residue or mass loss were produced from the recycling trials.

Figure 6: A CFRP laminate sample before recycling (a) and recycled carbon fibres (b).

3.3 Single fibre tensile strength

The single fibre tensile strength of each type of recycled carbon fibres was measured and compared with virgin fibres. The tensile strength of each type of virgin carbon fibres was measured in a previous study [14]. A 60.5% increase in the average tensile strength was observed in sample 1. This is not within expectation as the oxidative environment during char removal process will cause oxidation of carbon atoms in the fibres and lead to reduction of tensile strength. Further investigation into this case is required to understand the cause. Apart from sample 1, degradation of tensile strength was shown in sample 2 – 4. The reduction of single fibre tensile strength in sample 2-4 after recycling was on average 5.1%, 5.2% and 12.8%, respectively. Considering the uncertainties in the measurements, the strength reduction in sample 2 and 3 is minor. Sample 4, which had undergone both fibre surface treatments, exhibited more than twice the fibre tensile strength reduction in sample 2 and 3. However, it is difficult to determine if there are combined effects of the two fibre surface treatments during CFRP production on the tensile strength of recycled carbon fibres, given that sample 1 shows unexpected improvement in tensile strength after recycling.

Figure 7: Comparison between single fibre tensile strength of virgin CF and recycled CF.

4 CONCLUSION

An experimental study on four types of CFRPs was conducted to understand the impacts of two fibre surface treatments during CFRP production on the tensile strength of the recycled carbon fibres. The results show minor impacts of fibre surface oxidation in ammonium bicarbonate and sizing with epoxy

834 on the thermal degradation temperatures of the epoxy resin matrix and the fibres during the two-step pyrolysis recycling process. In contrast, a more significant variation (6.2%) was observed in the oxidation temperature of the pyrolytic char residue. Statistical analysis with a larger sample size is needed to determine the impact on the pyrolytic char residue. Fibre surface oxidation or sizing caused a minor reduction (5.2% and 5.8%) in the tensile strength of carbon fibres after recycling. The reduction in tensile strength more than doubled (12.8%) in fibres from CFRP subjected to both surface treatments.

Further work is necessary to determine whether the two fibre surface treatments in the production of CFRP will lead to inconsistent strength of recycled carbon fibres. The cause for the increase in fibre tensile strength in sample 1 needs to be understood, which will allow the comparison of recycled fibres from CFRP with and without fibre surface treatments. The potential combined effects of the two treatments will also be investigated. Moreover, this study only investigated fibre surface treatments with a particular choice of electrolyte (ammonium bicarbonate) for surface oxidation and a particular sizing agent (epoxy 834). Potential future work will be on broadening the investigation to other fibre surface treatment settings and understand the impact of these variations on the quality of recycled carbon fibres.

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